

Savremena psihijatrija i medicina / Contemporary Psychiatry & Medicine
2021: 3(2), str./pp. 2-18

UDK: 616.89-008.441-055.2

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5767579

Primljeno/received: 15.11.2021.

Prihvaćeno/accepted: 06.12.2021.

Original research paper

**PRELIMINARY VALIDATION OF
SCALE OF NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL AND
PSYCHIATRIC SYMPTOMS OF
POST-COVID-19 SYNDROME (SNP-PC19)
WITH INITIAL FINDINGS**

Selman Repišti

Clinical Center of Montenegro, Podgorica, Montenegro
selman9r@yahoo.com

Lidija Injac Stevović

Corresponding author

Faculty of Medicine, University of Montenegro;
Clinical Center of Montenegro, Podgorica, Montenegro
injacl19@gmail.com

Tamara Radojičić

Clinical Center of Montenegro, Podgorica, Montenegro
tamararadojicic11@gmail.com

Abstract

The first aim of the paper was to examine the psychometric properties of the SNP-PC19, a scale measuring the intensity and assessing the number of neuro-

psychological and psychiatric symptoms within post-COVID-19 syndrome. The second aim was to examine the severity and number of 15 symptoms included in the scale. Fifty-three participants (44 females), with a mean age of 38.45 ($SD = 9.58$), participated in the study. On average, they were infected by the coronavirus 6-7 months ago and experienced its main symptoms until 3-4 months ago. Most of them had not been treated for other chronic illnesses before being infected with COVID-19. The psychometric check revealed a unidimensional latent structure of the instrument, as well as its very good reliability and homogeneity. The second part of the findings includes tiredness (energy loss) which emerged as the most prominent and frequent symptom, mild to moderate severity of symptoms, and, on average, $M = 9.40$ ($Mdn = 11$) symptoms.

Key words: reliability, homogeneity, validity, post-COVID-19 syndrome, long COVID-19

INTRODUCTION

Background

According to the World Health Organization's statistics, by November 12th, there had been 251,788,329 confirmed cases of COVID-19 around the world, out of which 5,077,907 cases resulted in death (WHO, 2021). Most people, with appropriate medical treatments, manage to fully recover from COVID-19. Some people, however, experience various persistent or relapsing symptoms that can last for weeks or months after the organism has been cleared up from infection. The symptoms can include: a cough, a fever, a sore throat, breathlessness, fatigue, joint pain, nonspecific chest pain, cognitive blunting, skin rashes, diarrhea, sleep problems, anxiety, depression, etc. These residual effects of COVID-19 have been known as "long COVID-19", "post COVID-19 syndrome" or "post-acute COVID-19 syndrome". Apart from having negative effects on the overall life quality, post COVID-19 syndrome can also impact the functioning and social and personal lives of survivors, making it difficult for them to reintegrate into society and get back to their usual routines (Lemhöfer et al., 2021).

Mental health professionals and researchers have been especially concerned regarding the psychological and psychiatric consequences of COVID-19. After surviving COVID-19, a number of people are left with lingering anxiety, depression, and other mental health issues. Anxiety and depression proved to be among the predominant post COVID-19 symptoms (Penninx, 2021). Indeed, research evidence shows that COVID-19 survivors are at an increased risk of developing mood and anxiety disorders in the three months after infection. Moreover, subsequent neurological diagnoses have been shown to depend on the severity of COVID-19. The incidence of neurological and psychiatric outcomes was greater in patients who had experienced more than five COVID-19 symptoms and had to be hospitalized during illness (Taquet et al., 2021). Cognitive impairment, which manifests as difficulties with concentration, memory, receptive language, etc., has also been reported among COVID-19 survivors (Penninx, 2021).

There is some evidence that getting the vaccine could potentially reduce the incidence of post COVID-19 syndrome in people who have been infected before they were vaccinated. According to the reports from the Office for National Statistics, receiving the first dose of vaccine was associated with an initial 13% decrease in likelihood of self-reported post COVID-19 syndrome (Ayoubkhani & Bermingham, 2021).

Aims of the study

The first aim of the present study was to validate a tool for assessing the severity and number of neuropsychological and psychiatric symptoms that can occur during post-COVID-19 syndrome. The second aim was to investigate the intensity and number of these symptoms in a sample from the Balkans.

METHODS

Participants

Fifty-three people who had been infected by the coronavirus participated in the study, of which nine were males and 44 were females. Their mean age was $M = 38.45$ ($SD = 9.58$). The youngest participant was 20 and the oldest was

64. The other sociodemographics and some COVID-19 related features of the sample are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Sociodemographics and COVID-19 related characteristics

Variables	Descriptives
<i>Country of residence</i>	
Bosnia and Herzegovina	17
Serbia	13
Croatia	9
Montenegro	4
North Macedonia	2
Other (Austria, France, Germany and the USA)*	7
Missing data	1
<i>Level of education</i>	
Secondary education	11
Post-secondary education (2 years)	7
Post-secondary education (3+ years)	35
<i>When did you get the COVID-19 infection? (days)</i>	
M (SD)	202.34 (110.02)
Mdn** (P ₂₅ – P ₇₅)***	210 (120 – 300)
Range	13 – 370
<i>When did you stop feeling the main symptoms of the COVID-19 infection? (days)</i>	
M (SD)	127.53 (112.45)
Mdn (P ₂₅ – P ₇₅)	90 (15 – 200)
Range	0 – 350
<i>Have you been treated for a psychiatric, neurological, or other illness before getting infected with COVID-19?</i>	
Yes	6
No	47

* All of them were part of the Balkans diaspora; ** Median value; *** 25th and 75th percentile

Most participants were from Bosnia and Herzegovina ($n = 17$) and some of them were from the Balkans diaspora ($n = 7$). The largest portion of the sample completed some post-secondary education of three years or more ($n = 35$). On average, participants were infected by the coronavirus six to seven months ago. They stopped experiencing the main COVID-19 symptoms approximately three to four months ago. Vast majority of them had not been treated

for a psychiatric, neurological or other illness before they got infected with COVID-19.

Instruments

The instrument used in this study was the *Scale of Neuropsychological and Psychiatric Symptoms of Post-COVID-19 Syndrome (SNP-PC19)*; Repišti, Injac Stevović, & Radojičić, 2021). The scale consists of 15 items on a 5-point Likert-type scale (0 – 4). Total scores are calculated in two ways: (1) by summing up the scores on all items and dividing the sum by 15 (obtaining the average intensity of symptoms) and (2) by recoding every non-zero value into 1 and summing them up (obtaining the total number of symptoms). Greater scores indicate a greater intensity or number of neuropsychological and psychiatric symptoms within the post-COVID-19 syndrome.

Along with SNP-PC19, participants were asked to provide information on their gender, age, country of residence, and level of education, as well as to answer the following questions: "Are there any other problems (symptoms) not covered by the scale?", "When did you get the COVID-19 infection?", "When did you stop feeling the main symptoms of the COVID-19 infection, e.g. fever, headache, respiratory problems, etc.?", "Have you been treated for a psychiatric, neurological, or other illness before getting infected with COVID-19?" (if the answer was positive, participants were asked to list those illnesses), and "Were there other symptoms apart from those covered by the scale?"

Research procedures and data analysis

This was a cross-sectional study where convenience sampling was employed. It lasted from 1st of September to 1st of November 2021 via several social networks (Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn). The online form for the instrument was created using Google Forms, and the link was shared through the mentioned social networks.

Responses were recorded in a MS Excel database and transferred to SPSS for Win 25.0 (Trial version), where statistical and psychometric analyses were

conducted. Descriptive statistical values were calculated as well as Pearson’s coefficients of correlation. Within the psychometric check, the following procedures and calculations were conducted: Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin’s measure of sample adequacy (KMO), Bartlett’s test of sphericity, and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) in order to check the scale’s criterion validity as well as Cronbach’s alpha coefficient (α), Intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC), Guttman’s lambda-4 (recommended among various lambda coefficients by Guttman, 1945), and average/mean inter-item correlation (AIC/MIC) to check its internal consistency reliability and homogeneity.

RESULTS

Psychometric properties of the SNP-PC19

The exploratory factor analysis prerequisites were met ($KMO = .832$; $\chi^2(105) = 670.270$, $p < .001$). However, the sample size was small and did not meet the criterion of at least 300 participants (as recommended by e.g. Clark & Watson, 2019) nor the rule of thumb criterion of 100 or more participants (e.g. Hair, Anderson, Tatham, & Black, 1995). On the other hand, some other authors (e.g. Sarnas & Zeller, 2002) recommended a less strict criterion of 50 or more participants.

Initially, three components were extracted using Principal Component Analysis and the Kaiser-Guttman's criterion (> 1), accounting for 74.35% of the variance (Table 2).

Table 2. The extracted components and explained variance

Component	Eigenvalue (λ)	% of explained variance	Cumulative % of explained variance
1	8.492	56.612	56.612
2	1.529	10.197	66.809
3	1.131	7.539	74.348

However, the solution with three components was shown to be non-interpretative (mainly due to secondary factor loadings), as was the solution with the first two components. Taking this and the principle of parsimony into account, it was decided to retain the first extracted component, explaining

56.61% of the variance. In addition, based on Cattell's scree plot (Figure 1), either three components or a single component could be retained.

Figure 1. Cattell's scree plot

All items had sufficiently high communalities (ranging from $h^2 = .491$ for item no. 13 to $.914$ for item no. 1). As shown in Table 3, the lowest factor loading was obtained for item no. 13 ($r_{iF} = .504$) and the highest one for item no. 8 ($r_{iF} = .908$). All factor loadings were greater than $.45/.50$, as recommended for narrower scales (Clark & Watson, 2019), as was the case with our scale.

Table 3. Communalities and factor loadings of the items

Items	Communalities (h^2)	Factor loadings (r_{iF})
1. problems with concentration/ maintenance of attention	.914	.772
2. problems with memorizing	.851	.705

3. disorientation/confusion	.703	.722
4. sleeping problems	.584	.677
5. difficulties with performing several activities quickly and efficiently at the same time	.827	.754
6. feelings of sadness	.673	.802
7. feelings of hopelessness	.734	.723
8. feelings of disturbance	.851	.908
9. feelings of anxiety	.855	.883
10. feelings of fear	.743	.745
11. tiredness (energy loss)	.633	.668
12. slow motion (in thinking, speech and/or behaviour)	.767	.825
13. thoughts about suicide	.491	.504
14. losing patience/temper easily	.761	.739
15. frequent and/or sudden mood swings	.765	.775

Cronbach's alpha coefficient was .944 (based on standardized items, $\alpha = .943$). The results of the internal consistency check are displayed in Table 4.

Table 4. Internal consistency check

Items	Corrected item-total correlations	Squared multiple correlations	Cronbach's alpha if item deleted
1. problems with concentration/maintenance of attention	.732	.865	.940
2. problems with memorizing	.659	.826	.942
3. disorientation/confusion	.670	.732	.942
4. sleeping problems	.634	.628	.943
5. difficulties with performing several activities quickly and efficiently at the same time	.719	.781	.940
6. feelings of sadness	.764	.751	.939
7. feelings of hopelessness	.672	.647	.941
8. feelings of disturbance	.884	.918	.936
9. feelings of anxiety	.856	.890	.937
10. feelings of fear	.708	.735	.941

11. tiredness (energy loss)	.623	.518	.943
12. slow motion (in thinking, speech and/or behaviour)	.790	.809	.939
13. thoughts about suicide	.453	.515	.946
14. losing patience/temper easily	.687	.800	.941
15. frequent and/or sudden mood swings	.726	.816	.940

The corrected item-total correlations were moderate to high and ranged from .453 (item no. 13) to .884 (item no. 8). Squared multiple correlations (SMCs), which indicate the common variance of a particular item with the other items, ranged from .515 (item no. 13) to .918 (item no. 8). By deleting item no. 13, alpha coefficient will rise to .946. However, the item is an indicator of an important criterion (i.e. suicide risk). Hence, it was retained.

Other indicators of internal consistency of the scale had very high values – $ICC = .944$ (95% CI: .920 – .964) and Guttman's $\lambda_4 = .934$. The average inter-item correlation (AIC) was .527 and reflected a very good homogeneity of the instrument.

Main findings

The mean value for each item is shown in Figure 2. The most prominent (i.e. intense) symptoms were tiredness / loss of energy ($M = 2.51$), feelings of anxiety ($M = 1.60$), and difficulties with performing several activities quickly and efficiently at the same time, i.e. multitasking performance ($M = 1.58$). The least intense symptoms were: thoughts about suicide ($M = 0.32$), disorientation/confusion ($M = 0.94$), and feelings of hopelessness ($M = 0.96$). An additional finding was that the range of scores for each item was the same as the theoretical one. In other words, the lowest obtained score was 0, whereas the highest one was 4.

Figure 2. Average scores on the items

As shown in Table 5, the most common symptom was tiredness/energy loss ($f = 50$), followed by feelings of anxiety and fear ($f = 40$ and 39 , respectively). The least common symptom was thoughts about suicide ($f = 9$), followed by disorientation/confusion, feelings of hopelessness, and losing patience/temper easily (sharing the same rank and each with $f = 30$).

Table 5. The symptoms ranked by the frequency of their occurrence/reporting

Symptoms	f
• Tiredness/energy loss	50
• Feelings of anxiety	40
• Feelings of fear	39
• Difficulties with performing several activities quickly and efficiently at the same time	38

• Feelings of disturbance	37
• Frequent and/or sudden mood swings	
• Problems with concentration/maintenance of attention	36
• Slow motion (in thinking, speech and/or behaviour)	
• Problems with memorizing	34
• Sleeping problems	
• Feelings of sadness	33
• Disorientation/confusion	
• Feelings of hopelessness	30
• Losing patience/temper easily	
• Thoughts about suicide	9

Descriptive statistical values calculated based on the results on the whole scale, are shown in Table 6. The range of symptoms' intensity was almost the same as the theoretical one, and the range of the number of symptoms was equal to the theoretical one for this type of score. The mean value of the intensity of symptoms was $M = 1.34$, that is, they burdened participants poorly to moderately. Half of the participants scored between 0.53 and 2. The average number of symptoms ($M = 9.49$) was higher than expected (the theoretical mean was 7.5), and much higher when estimated by using the median value ($Mdn = 11$). Fifty percent of participants reported five to 15 symptoms.

Table 6. Descriptives for the whole scale

Scores	Range	$M (SD)$	$Mdn (P_{25} - P_{75})$
Intensity of symptoms	0 – 3.93	1.34 (0.97)	1.20 (0.53 – 2.00)
Number of symptoms	0 – 15	9.40 (4.86)	11.00 (5.00 – 14.00)

Correlations of participants' scores on SNP-C19 and other variables included in this study are displayed in Table 7. It can be noticed that age was in a weak positive and statistically significant correlation with number of symptoms ($r = .275, p < .05$). The time since the cessation of the main COVID-19 symptoms had a moderately negative and statistically significant correlation with the number of symptoms ($r = .386, p < .001$) and a borderline significant correlation with the intensity of symptoms ($r = -.277, p = .054$).

Table 7. Correlations of SNP-C19 scores with gender, age, level of education, and some COVID-19-related variables

	Intensity of symptoms	Number of symptoms
Gender	-.067	-.057
Age	.037	.275*
Level of education	-.220	-.070
When did you get the COVID-19 infection?	.008	-.098
When did you stop feeling the main symptoms of the COVID-19 infection?	-.277	-.386**
Have you been treated for a psychiatric, neurological or other illness before getting infected with COVID-19?	-.025	-.134

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$

Additional findings

This part of the results includes illnesses, i.e., mental and physical health issues, for which participants have been treated before getting infected with COVID-19. They were: asthma, depression, hyperthyroidism, panic attacks, and posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD).

Additionally, participants were asked to provide some symptoms (problems) not covered by the scale. Their responses, mostly reflecting neurological, respiratory and cardiovascular issues, were: ageusia, anosmia, alopecia, breathing difficulties, dizziness, dry skin, gynecological problems, headaches, heart arrhythmias, hypertension, myalgia, shortness of breath, stabbing pain in the chest and tremor.

DISCUSSION

The paper dealt with psychometric properties of the SNP-PC19 as well as the intensity and number of symptoms assessed with this instrument.

Based on PCA, the scale is a unidimensional instrument. The latent dimension represents the neuropsychological and psychiatric cluster of symptoms within post-COVID-19 syndrome. The extracted dimension is best defined in terms of disturbance, anxiety, and three slow-motion symptoms (bradypsychia/

bradyphrenia, bradylalia, and bradykinesia). Disturbance is primarily an aspect of neuroticism or anxiety. Slow motion can result from various conditions, such as depression, schizophrenia, and physical illnesses.

Reliability check revealed a high level of internal consistency of the instrument and, according to Cicchetti (1994), the obtained value of Cronbach's alpha coefficient could be labelled as "excellent". Other coefficients that were used as indicators of internal consistency (ICC and Guttman's λ_4) were also high. ICCs above .90 are considered "excellent" as well (Portney & Watkins, 2000). Furthermore, average inter-item correlation (AIC) indicated a high level of homogeneity of the scale. The recommended range of acceptable values of AIC is .15 to .50 (Briggs & Cheek, 1986) and its value in the present study appeared to be slightly above .50. Hence, other researchers who would like to use this scale could omit several items with a negligible reduction in homogeneity of the scale. By doing so, however, its content validity could be diminished.

The main findings suggested that tiredness (loss of energy), anxiety, and multitasking performance were the most prominent symptoms. Loss of energy, in the context of psychiatry, could be experienced due to depression. Next, symptoms of anxiety constitute a self-explanatory cluster of symptoms. In line with that, the second most frequent symptom (fear and anxiety) could be regarded as fear influenced by negative anticipation of events that could occur in the future. High levels of depression, anxiety and fear during the COVID-19 pandemic were found in a study conducted by Rodríguez-Hidalgo, Pantaleón, Dios, and Falla (2020). Lastly, successful multitasking performance requires a capacity for dealing with divided attention, coupled with a certain degree of psychomotor skills, and controlled by executive functions. According to Burgess, Veitch, de Lacy Costello and Shallice (2000), planning (including plan-following) as well as retrospective and prospective memory are cognitive functions relevant for multitasking. Hence, poor performance in this domain could be linked to deficits in attention, psychomotor, memory, and executive functions.

Other findings are in line with the previous ones because physical problems (e.g. shortness of breath, muscle pain) could lead to the feeling of energy loss and anxiety. An interplay of physical and mental health issues is probably a core feature of post-COVID-19 syndrome.

Strengths and limitations

The participants were from different countries and belonged to different age groups, representing various populations. These are the two main strengths of the study.

The main limitations of the study were its sample size and the under-representation of males in it. Another limitation is the type of instrument. It is a self-report measure and objective measures such as, e.g., instruments assessing memory, attention, multitasking performance, etc., will result in more valid and realistic estimates of participants' symptoms. Additionally, the neuropsychological and psychiatric cluster of symptoms as part of the post-COVID syndrome could, to some extent, emerge from previously undiagnosed mental health issues.

Recommendations and future directions

The scale can be used in both clinical practice and research. Within clinical practice, the instrument could be part of the psychological assessment and psychiatric examination of people who have had the COVID-19 infection. It can also be used for follow-up of patients' conditions.

In terms of future research directions, the SNP-PC19 should be validated on larger samples with roughly equal representation of males and females. In addition, it would be useful to determine a cut-off score for the severity of symptoms, which would help clinicians decide whether a person needs some regular treatment (non-pharmacological and/or pharmacological).

REFERENCES

Ayoubkhani, D. & Bermingham, C. (2021). Coronavirus (COVID-19) vaccination and self-reported long COVID in the UK. Office for National Statistics,

<https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/healthandso>

- cialcare/conditionsanddiseases/articles/coronaviruscovid19vaccinationandselfreportedlongcovidintheuk/25october2021 (15/11/2021)
- Briggs, S. R. & Cheek, J. M. (1986). The role of factor analysis in the development and evaluation of personality scales. *Journal of Personality*, 54, 106–148.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6494.1986.tb00391>
- Burgess, P. W., Veitch, E., de Lacy Costello, A., & Shallice, T. (2000). The cognitive and neuroanatomical correlates of multitasking. *Neuropsychologia*, 38 (6), 848–863.
- Cicchetti, D. V. (1994). Guidelines, criteria, and rules of thumb for evaluating normed and standardized assessment instruments in psychology. *Psychological Assessment*, 6(4), 284–290.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/1040-3590.6.4.284>
- Clark, L. A. & Watson, D. (2019). Constructing validity: New developments in creating objective measuring instruments. *Psychological Assessment*, 31(12), 1412–1427. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pas0000626>
- Guttman, L. A. (1945). A basis for analyzing test-retest reliability. *Psychometrika*, 10, 255–282.
- Hair, J. F., Anderson, R. E., Tatham, R. L., & Black, W. C. (1995). *Multivariate data analysis* (4th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Lemhöfer, C., Sturm, C., Loudovici-Krug, D., Best, N. & Gutenbrunner, C. (2021). The impact of post COVID syndrome on functioning – results from a community survey in patients after mild and moderate SARS-CoV-2-infections in Germany. *Journal of Occupational Medicine and Toxicology*, 16(45), 1-9.
- Penninx, W.J.H.B. (2021). Psychiatric symptoms and cognitive impairment in long COVID: the relevance of immunopsychiatry. *World Psychiatry*, 20(3), 357-358.
- Portney, L. G. & Watkins, M. P. (2000). *Foundations of clinical research: applications to practice*. New Jersey: prentice Hall.
- Repišti, S., Injac Stevović, L., & Radojčić, T. (2021). Scale of Neurological and Psychiatric Symptoms within the post-COVID-19 syndrome: A pilot study. *Savremena psihijatrija i medicina [Contemporary Psychiatry & Medicine]*, 3(1), 46-55.

- Rodríguez-Hidalgo, A. J., Pantaleón, Y., Dios, I., & Falla, D. (2020). Fear of COVID-19, stress, and anxiety in University Undergraduate Students: A predictive model for depression. *Frontiers in Psychology, 11*, 591797. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.591797>
- Sapnas, K. G. & Zeller, R. A. (2002). Minimizing sample size when using exploratory factor analysis for measurement. *Journal of Nursing Measurement, 10*(2), 135–153. doi:10.1891/jnum.10.2.135.52552
- Taquet, M., Gedders, R.J., Husain, M., Luciano, S. & Harrison, J.P. (2021). 6-month neurological and psychiatric outcomes in 236 379 survivors of COVID-19: a retrospective cohort study using electronic health records. *Lancet Psychiatry, 8*, 416-27.
- World Health Organization (WHO) official website: <https://covid19.who.int/> (15/11/2021)

**PRELIMINARNA VALIDACIJA
SKALE NEUROPSIHOLOŠKIH I PSIHIJATRIJSKIH SIMPTOMA U
OKVIRU POST-COVID-19 SINDROMA (SNP-PC19)
I PRVI REZULTATI**

Selman Repišti

Lidija Injac Stevović

Tamara Radojičić

Sažetak

Prvi cilj rada bio je ispitivanje psihometrijskih karakteristika SNP-PC19, skale kojom se procjenjuje intenzitet i mjeri broj neuropsiholoških i psihijatrijskih simptoma u okviru post-COVID-19 sindroma. Drugi cilj bio je ispitivanje ozbiljnosti i broja 15 simptoma uključenih u ovu skalu. Pedeset tri ispitanika (44 ženskog pola), prosječne dobi od 38.45 ($SD = 9.58$) učestvovalo je u ovoj studiji. U prosjeku, koronavirusom su inficirani prije 6-7 mjeseci, a glavne simptome su prestali osjećati prije 3-4 mjeseca. Većina njih nisu liječeni od neke hronične bolesti prije COVID-19 infekcije. Psihometrijskom provjerom

utvrđeno je da je instrument unidimenzionalan, te da posjeduje veoma dobru pouzdanost i homogenost. Drugi dio rezultata odnosi se na to da je umor (gubitak energije) bio najprominentniji i najčešći simptom, da su simptomi bili blagi do umjereni i da je njihov prosječan broj iznosio $M = 9.40$ ($Mdn = 11$).

Ključne riječi: pouzdanost, homogenost, valjanost, post-COVID-19 sindrom, produženi COVID-19